

EUCLID RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Selby****FIRST NAME: Jessica****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

RIDING A BIKE AGAIN

1) INTRODUCTION

Entering the doctorate program in international public health at Euclid University is quite an exciting endeavor. Having taken a leave of absence from formal academic studies for over seven years, it feels like learning to ride a bike again. A common expression in the United States (US), meaning once you have learned a skill (in this case, academic writing) it cannot be forgotten. An initial scan of the study materials for the first doctorate-level course with Euclid University ACA-401D International Academic Writing makes it possible to start with an encouraging outlook. The study materials are a compilation of tools and references to aide new students with academic writing. While it is reasonable to assume that doctoral-level students have basic knowledge and proficiency in writing essays, proper use of grammar and citing references correctly, it is important to recognize that Euclid University students come from a variety of cultural and literary backgrounds and may not have familiarity with the writing standards expected by Euclid University. This course attempts to orient and acclimatize new students to the writing and referencing expectations of Euclid University. The study materials provide an overview of essay writing, proper use of grammar, punctuation, plagiarism, citations, referencing, use of style guides, differences between American and British English, information about Latin abbreviation and expressions, and finally examples of corrections applied to written papers. It appears the overall goal of the information is to bring the doctoral student back to the fundamental principles of writing and to set forth the writing expectations specific to Euclid University.

2) WRITING STRATEGIES

Threaded throughout the study packet are references addressing strategies on how to develop well-written essays. Again, having been away from writing for an academic setting for an extended time, I appreciate revisiting basic principles of writing an essay. One of the items I found most helpful was an abbreviated list of basic steps to writing an essay (EUCLID 2015, 2). This list provided an easy to follow map of putting together a well-written paper. It was helpful remembering how to approach planning to write an essay. Writing an essay, particularly a good essay, is a dynamic interactive process that requires planning, organizing one's thoughts and is purposeful. Each of these aspects is fluid and occur throughout the writing process in no specific sequence. Having such a list will be a very helpful resource moving forward in writing papers for school. These noted steps applied in the writing and rewriting of this assignment.

3) UNIFORMITY

Additional highly emphasized points addressed in the study material are the uniform expectations of how assignments are formatted, submitted and, referenced. For example, specific EUCLID Word templates (EUCLID 2015, 6) are requirements for use for written assignments referred to as Response Papers (RP) and Major Papers (MP). Another example of how uniformity is applied is how assignment file names are to be electronically saved (EUCLID 2015, 7). There are a few reasons why this type of uniformity is the standard. It provides the writer an outline of methodically organizing written information. It also allows the evaluator of written assignments to follow a consistent sequence of expected information. This standard will help me in how I establish the components of papers that I will be writing for school. It is very helpful to have this information reviewed so early on in my coursework.

4) CHANGING STYLES

Citing sources appropriately and formatting citations and their references correctly are also topics reiterated. It never occurred to me how many different styles there were to citing references. In the US in my previous academic work I typically used the American Psychological Association (APA) or Modern Language Association of America (MLA) styles for citing references. The Turabian style is a new system of citing source information to me. I was able to grasp the application of Turabian style by having a basic understanding of what it is. "While sometimes reference is made to a "Turabian style," this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers" (EUCLID 2015, 66). As I was reading the CMS Crib Sheet provided in the packet, it was interesting to note that while the structure of the citations is new information the rules of writing are not. For example, an epiphany I had while reading this section in the packet about the Turabian style was that the writing structure I have learned and adapted over the years as it applies to the use of acronyms, quotations and page formatting is considered Turabian style. I attribute this

to years of having to write for college and reading large numbers of publications during my studies. I value how this twelve-page section of the packet takes a comprehensive approach in highlighting the essentials of Turabian style especially, for a new doctoral student looking towards publishing research in the future.

5) GIVING CREDIT WHERE CREDIT IS DUE

It is impossible to write about applying proper citations without addressing the topic of plagiarism. I value how the packet included information about plagiarism and the explanation of how citations and plagiarism are interrelated. A writer runs the risk of plagiarism if not applying proper use of citations. While I am familiar with the information about what plagiarism is, the explanation of citing references for the sake of citing references and not to strengthen one's argument or purpose in an essay was a different perspective for me. I assumed that the use of citations was to validate and support a writer's viewpoint. This information leads me to believe writers may take liberty in unnecessarily citing information. The course packet was helpful in addressing when not to cite. "When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas you do not need to cite its source" (EUCLID 2015, 30).

6) BUILDING BLOCKS OF SENTENCE STRUCTURE

The packet also goes into detail about emphasizing grammar and punctuation. In the packet section titled Lit-101 Review some of the information I already knew and applied to my current writing practices and some was new and thought-provoking. For example, the explanation of how many spaces go after a period was interesting. "The current opinion is one space should be typed after any punctuation" (EUCLID 2015, 47). This statement left me wondering how many typed spaces do go after a period. I will admit that leaving two typed spaces after a period, I learned in a typing class thirty years ago and have honestly never veered from that formatting until I read this noted information. Another area of interest in reviewing grammar and punctuation was the use of the word "and" in the beginning of a sentence. "When used purposefully and appropriately, starting a sentence with a conjunction can be a powerful or rhetorical stylistic tool" (EUCLID 2015, 50). This information will help me to be cognizant of the use of a conjunction at the beginning of a sentence. Moving forward while I am reading various materials, I hope to better learn how seasoned writers integrate the use of conjunctions at the beginning of a sentence. Overall, this section was a helpful consolidated list to review and made me reconsider use of grammar and punctuation in my writing.

7) AMERICA VERSUS BRITAIN

Another area in the reading packet that further expanded on the topic of punctuation was in review of the differences between American and British English. It never occurred to me previously that there was even a difference between American and British English. Having gone to college only in the US it had not been necessary for my previous studies to have known the differences. It was interesting to read about the reasons why American English is more prevailing than British English. One reason that resonated with me was the “appeal of the American popular culture on language and habits” (EUCLID 2015, 54). American popular culture is constantly changing, and I was reminded of the influence the United States has on the rest of the world. I do appreciate the section highlighting these language differences being integrated into the course packet and am humbled that the academic program I have embarked upon with Euclid University is one delivered from an international perspective. It will be necessary to have a basic understanding and knowledge of these language differences. In reviewing this section much of the written language was familiar. I was taken aback by the politically incorrect and explicit terms (EUCLID 2015, 58) used as examples of language differences. I remember after the initial reading of this section wondering why these were the chosen examples. The rationale I could come up with was that I could be reviewing research or conducting qualitative research where these words could be the responses of research participants and therefore would be important for me to know what the meanings were.

8) CONCLUSION

Not knowing what to expect as I started the first doctorate-level course with Euclid University ACA-401D International Academic Writing I was pleasantly surprised to start with a review of the fundamentals of academic writing. It has been a long time since I have written my last academic essay and appreciated a class that would help me refresh my memory of the basics of writing and prompt me to apply these methods firsthand again for an academic audience. Writing the Response Paper was initially a bit of a challenge in trying to organize my thoughts about the study materials and respond to them in writing. I do value being able to respond independently with my thoughts about the subject matter and formulate question about the information presented. The study material in the course packet I believe equips me with being able to start the doctoral level program with Euclid University successfully.

REFERENCE

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed September 6, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.